

TEACHING ENGLISH TO CIVIL ENGINEERING STUDENTS THROUGH THE COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada til o'qituvchilariga kommunikativ tilni o'rgatish tamoyillarini o'rganishga yo'l-yo'riq berish va ularni o'qitishda tatbiq etishning mumkin bo'lgan usullarini taqdim etishdan iborat. Taqdim etilgan misollar va dars mashg'ulotlar namunalari ingliz tili o'qituvchilariga o'z kontekstida kommunikativ tilni o'rgatish tamoyillaridan foydalanishda yordam beradi. Maqolaning nazariy va amaliy ahamiyati, kommunikativ tilni o'rgatishni darslarda qanday amalga oshirish mumkinligini ko'rsatadigan til topshiriqlari va mashg'ulotlar yordamida nazariyani amaliyotga qanday kiritish mumkinligini ko'rsatishdir.

Kalit so'zlar: haqiqiy materiallar, to'rtta ko'nikma, o'qish yozish tinglash nutq usuli, lingvistik, sotsiolingvistik, pragmatik, strategik, kompetensiyalar.

Annotation. In the given article is to give language teachers direction in exploring the principles of CLT and present the possible ways of implementing them in their teaching. The presented examples and samples of lesson and activities help teachers of English in using the principles of CLT in their context. Theoretical and practical value of the article is to demonstrate how theory can be brought into practice with the help of language tasks and activities that illustrate how CLT can be implemented in classes.

Keywords: authentic materials, four skills, reading writing listening speaking method. linguistic, sociolinguistic, pragmatic, strategic, competencies.

In Uzbekistan, English has been applied for any levels. It has been applied from kindergarten up to college. It means that, English is not something new in our country. Many people use it to communicate each other in daily life.

It is known within institutions of higher education that English is taught as a separate subject matter in almost all university fields. Besides, teachers fulfilling this task design the content of language courses by themselves because administrative authorities do not provide them with syllabuses to guide them in what to teach and how. Nowadays it is highly related to effective teaching in a way that a key aspect of effective teaching is having a plan for what will happen in the classroom. It is said that a great deal of the teacher effectiveness has to do with the ability to design Lesson Plans, since Preparation is the most important thing a teacher does.[1].

It is clear that all ESP teachers have difficulties in creating CLT in their lessons as me. As we know, ESP focuses on obtaining some professional skills, particular job-related functions as well as the specific needs of the learners. Due to learners' levels I come across such kind of issues. In spite of their lack of knowledge, I attempt to challenge them to learn and speak in target language. My students also mixed-level students. I have faced different challenges in teaching different professions and nonlinguistic. Some of my students do not know even the English alphabet and they asked me let us learn English from the beginning. However, we have a special program and we cannot get out of it, can we?

From the first lesson I use in my classes not only one skill, no matter what, the result of learning English in ESP groups is usually not successful. As a teacher with a little experience in the field of engineers of polytechnic sphere, I prepare the materials for my classes, use information from the Internet. Then I tried to use different interactive methods during my lesson. For example: If I asked new words for the lesson, I used a "Hot potato" method group work", "pair work" or "matching" methods. I try use different texts for different reading tasks. I don't ask student to read aloud in class to test their comprehension. When reading aloud, the reader focuses on pronunciation, not comprehension. In any case, listening to other students' inaccurate reading is boring and counterproductive. I ask students read silently when reading is to be done in class. Students are able to scan a passage quickly to find specific information and increasing large vocabulary.

To recapitulate we must not deny traditional methods of teaching. All teachers should be skillful enough to combine different methods and approaches to make their lesson more productive.

Our lessons form on an assessment of purposes and needs and the functions for which English is involved. In fact, our English lessons should focus on more on language in context than on teaching grammar and language structures. The focal point of our lessons is that English is not taught as a subject separated from the learners' real world instead it is integrated into a subject matter area important to the users. Teachers should activate students to apply what they learn in English classes to their main field of study. Being able to use the vocabulary and structures that they study in a meaningful context supports what is taught and develops their motivation. The students' abilities in their fields make better their ability to acquire English. In groups oriented to ESP group students, I give authentic materials for improving students' listening, reading, writing and speaking abilities. Matching activities and jigsaw-reading technic contributes to them to catch main idea of the context. Students also do tasks like reading for gist and catching main idea of the context. Such kind of activities help them to improve and develop their language competence.

In my opinion, the most important skills are listening and speaking. Because they are used more than others are. Students should be able to communicate in the real life. In a real situation, a student must first listen and then try to convey his ideas. We use reading and writing in everyday, but in many ways, it is very important for scientific purposes. These four methods are also very important for people with language proficiency (student, teacher, etc.).

To my way of thinking, if we look at the demand today, vocabulary and speech are in the first place, but the pronunciation is also very important. Grammar and translation are important to the classical method, but the traditional method does not ignore it. During my lessons I try to use CLT (Communicative Language teaching) approach as that consists of linguistic, sociolinguistic, pragmatic and strategic competencies. This methodological approach has been proved to develop students' thinking abilities, through which they themselves get to know about rules, facts and meanings, they generate their own knowledge on how to communicate appropriately in different real-life situations

I have a lesson on the topic " Construction equipment ". The main goal of my lessons is to enlarge the students' vocabulary and teach how to use them in situations. In my lessons I use strategic approach to explain the vocabulary.

Firstly, I have chosen the warm up and gave some questions. According to picture the students should find the suitable words. Then I wanted to consolidate the vocabulary through the pictures and asking questions to each other's. The students did their best. They have learned the

main idea of the activity through showing the picture. Then, I presented some information about equipment. Then I taught the new words according to the pictures. After taking some information on the engineering equipment, I divided the students into three groups. The students wrote down the name of the machines in a mind map. Secondly, I gave some pictures then my students described every machine through modal verbs can and may. Then every group member presented their machines to other groups by explaining its meaning and making up sentences for it. Then they listened one exercise and Ss completed the descriptions of construction site equipment then put one word in each gap. After listening I checked their answer. Positives: The educational process in the lesson was good. The students are active and energetic. They tried to work cooperatively and developed their vocabulary and integrated skills. Areas to improve: I should use more interesting activities to improve student's linguistic competences and their communicative.

So, I should have to improve my students' integrated skills through communicative language teaching approaches. As I am an ESP teacher, I should have to pay attention to the improvement of student's vocabulary reserve and their integrated skills like listening, reading, writing and speaking. That is improving of student's vocabulary range related to their field of study. I have to mention is that, I could have solved the problem of students' critical thinking and communicative competence. So, I tried to implement strategic approach. In future I am going to use pragmatic and sociolinguistic approaches. In my lesson in order to develop my students' good points and get rid of their weak points. I discussed possible problems my students' face and how we could prevent these from happening owning the future lessons. Teaching through the CLT doing activities based on with strategic approach I can get rid of students' communicative problems.

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